

Prediction of House Prices in Lagos-Nigeria Using Machine Learning Models

Mmesoma Peace Nwankwo

Department of Statistics, Faculty of Physical Sciences, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria

Ndukaku Macdonald Onyeizu

Department of Computer Science, Faculty of Physical Sciences, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria

Emmanuel Chibuogu Asogwa

Department of Computer Science, Faculty of Physical Sciences, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria

Chukwuogo Okwuchukwu Ejike

Department of Computer Science, Faculty of Physical Sciences, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria

Okechukwu J. Obulezi

Department of Statistics, Faculty of Physical Sciences, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria

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Abstract:

This paper considers the relationship between the price of houses and the features namely the number of bedrooms, parking space, and different house types. In this study, a machine learning approach was used to develop prediction models that predicted house prices in Lagos. Different machine learning techniques were used, train-test split to split the data into training sets for training and building the model and test data to test the accuracy of the model, performance metric mean absolute error to set the baseline for the model, Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) to help remove multicollinearity between features and Streamlit interactive dashboards to

communicate with the model. Correlation and regression methods were used to examine the relationship and build the model. It is observed that there is a strong positive correlation between the number of bedrooms and the number of toilets, likewise the number of bedrooms and the number of bathrooms. It also shows that there is a moderate positive correlation between the number of bedrooms and price. The model shows that the number of bedrooms, parking spaces, and house types play an important role in determining the price of houses.

Keywords: *Train-test split, Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), Correlation, Ridge regression, Machine learning.*

Introduction

Different factors affect the price of houses in Nigeria, states, towns, and localities depending on choice. An increasing factor in a particular state might be a decreasing factor in another state. Lagos known as the commercial capital of

Nigeria is known for its expensive house price, according to forbes.com it is ranked the 55 th most expensive city to live in the world. Ajah a suburb in Lagos state, is considered one of the best places to start a family. Unlike other areas such as Lekki, Ikoyi, and Victoria Island, Ajah is

a mix of both upper-class and middle-class citizens.

Machine learning (ML) is the subset of artificial intelligence (AI) that focuses on building systems that learn or improve performance based on the data they consume. There are basically three types of machine learning: supervised, unsupervised, and reinforcement learning. Supervised learning is effective for a variety of business purposes, including sales forecasting, inventory optimization, and fraud detection. Some examples of use cases include:

- Predicting real estate prices
- Classifying whether bank transactions are fraudulent or not
- Finding disease risk factors
- Determining whether loan applicants are low-risk or high-risk
- Predicting the failure of industrial equipment's mechanical parts

Regression is a supervised learning technique that aims to find the relationships between the dependent and independent variables. Ridge regression is a method of estimating the coefficients of multiple regression models in scenarios where the independent variables are highly correlated (Hilt, & Seegrist, 1977). It has been used in many fields including econometrics, chemistry, and engineering (Gruber, & Schucany, 2020). Uzoma, & Jeremiah, (2016) developed outlier detection and optimal variable selection techniques in regression analysis and other fascinating papers by the authors include (Anabike et al., 2023; Innocent et al., 2023; Abuh, Onyeagu, & Obulezi, 2023a; Abuh, Onyeagu, & Obulezi, 2023b; Obulezi et al., 2022; Onyekwere, & Obulezi, 2022; Onyekwere et al., 2022).

The ridge estimator is given as

$$\hat{\beta}_R = (X^T X + \lambda I)^{-1} X^T y \quad (1)$$

where y is the regressand, \mathbf{X} is the design matrix, I is the identity matrix and $\lambda \geq 0$ serves as the

constant shifting diagonals of the moment matrix.

Literature review

This section summarizes the concept of relevant work on Prediction of House Prices in Lagos-Nigeria using Machine Learning Models using a machine learning model. Here, the House price prediction can be divided into two categories (Zulkifley et al., 2020), first by focusing on house characteristics, and secondly by focusing on the model used in house price prediction. Many researchers have produced a house price prediction model, including Temur, Akgün, & Temur, (2019), Jafari, & Akhavian, (2019), Gao et al. (2022), The Danh Phan (2018), Yu et al. (2016) etc.

Byeonghwa (2015) implemented machine learning algorithms for housing price prediction accuracy. The housing data was analyzed from townhouses in Fairfax Country and compared the classification accuracy performance of various algorithms. To help a real estate agent, he then developed a better prediction model for enhanced decisions based on house price assessment.

Jafari and Akhavian (2019) stated that the square footage of a unit of a house is the most important variable in predicting the price of a house, followed by the number of bathrooms and number of bedrooms.

Raga Madhuri, Anuradha, & Vani Pujitha, (2019) discussed diverse regression techniques such as Gradient boosting and AdaBoost Regression, Ridge, Elastic Net, Multiple linear, and LASSO to locate the most excellent. The performance measures used are Mean Square Error (MSE) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE).

The rest of this paper is organized as follows; In section 3, we present the material and method. Here, the big data is cleaned for subsequent use. In section 4, we analyze the data and discussed the results in section 5. We then conclude the paper in section 6.

Material and Method

The dataset used for this analysis is the Nigerian housing dataset retrieved from Kaggle containing 25 unique states, 189 unique towns, and 24326 rows with 8 columns. After cleaning the data Ajah-Lagos was chosen as the town of interest.

Model

In the course of the analysis, certain libraries in Python were employed to model and analyze the data. Panda was used to read, clean, and manipulate the data, Scikit-learn (Sklearn) is an important library in Python that provide tools for machine learning algorithm for regression problem, classification problem, and clustering. Ridge regression was used for prediction to help reduce overfitting and multicollinearity, (Akinwande, Dikko & Gulumbe 2015). Multicollinearity arises when there is a correlation between the independent variables' percentages to help reduce this VIF was employed. The computational formula for VIF is given as

$$VIF = \frac{1}{1-R^2} \quad (2)$$

Correlation analysis is primarily concerned with finding out whether a relationship exists between variables and then determining the magnitude and action of that relationship.

$$\rho = \frac{n\sum xy - \sum x \sum y}{\sqrt{(n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2)(n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2)}} \quad (3)$$

Matplotlib and plotly express were used for data visualization.

Data cleaning

Figure 1 Shows the prices of houses in different states in Nigeria, It shows that Lagos state has the most expensive house followed by Abuja.

We can also see that in different towns in Nigeria, Ikoyi houses seem more expensive than in any other town, not only that but the gap between Ikoyi and any other house was too much, houses in Ifako-Ijaiye can't be in the league of houses in Maitama-District, which could be a result of outliers.

A low standard deviation shows that the data points tend to be close to their mean and vice-versa. However, from this it is noticed that the value of std is high are far away from the mean. This is to say we have outliers that contributed to this.

Figure 1. 20 Most Expensive Houses in Nigeria [N100m]

Figure 2. 20 Most Expensive Houses in Nigeria by Town

An outlier is a data point that is significantly different from the rest of the data. Boxplot helps identify outliers, it is located outside the whiskers. In fig 4, it shows that some data points are far away from each other, we have a house selling at approximately 1.8 trillion naira.

```

count      2.432600e+04
mean       3.013802e+08
std        1.220403e+10
min        9.000000e+04
25%        5.200000e+07
50%        8.500000e+07
75%        1.600000e+08
max        1.800000e+12
Name: price, dtype: float64

```

Figure 3. Descriptive Statistics for Price

Figure 4. Boxplot of House Prices

It was noticed that a house in Ikoyi Lagos was selling at N1.8 trillion and a house in Ifako-Ijaiye was selling at N55 billion. Whether these are true, we don't know but it affected our dataset and needs to be dropped. Using quantiles to trim the dataset, to contain data points between the 10th percentile and 90th percentile, changing the total number of dataset contained, having 19774 rows with the 8 columns.

```

bedrooms          9.0
bathrooms         9.0
toilets           9.0
parking_space     9.0
title             Terraced Duplexes
town              Ikoyi
state             Lagos
price            180000000000.0
dtype: object
bedrooms          7.0
bathrooms         8.0
toilets           8.0
parking_space     8.0
title             Terraced Bungalow
town              Ifako-Ijaiye
state             Lagos
price            55000000000.0
dtype: object

```

Figure 5. Outliers

```

Lagos          15580
Abuja          2768
Rivers         379
Oyo            262
Imo            210
Ogun           184
Enugu          115
Anambara       98
Edo            69
Delta          49
Akwa Ibom      14
Kaduna         9
Abia           7
Ekiti          7
Osun           4
Kogi           4
Kwara          4
Nasarawa       4
Kano           2
Borno          2
Plateau        1
Bayelsa        1
Niger          1
Name: state, dtype: int64

```

Figure 6. Number of Data Points in Each State

Using the value-count function in Python, to count the number of data points contained in each state, showing that Lagos contains the highest number of data points, trimming this series to contain series with data points greater than 100 using a function in Python. This resulted to fig 7.

```

Lagos          15580
Abuja          2768
Rivers         379
Oyo            262
Imo            210
Ogun           184
Enugu          115
Name: state, dtype: int64

```

Figure 7. Stabilizing the Data with Records Greater than 100

After cleaning the dataset, fig17 shows the mean price of an apartment, with Lagos still leading the chart.

Comparing fig 9 and Figure 2, we still see Ikoyi leading the chart but not far away from Maitama district.

Ajah ranks 24th from the chart with Ikoyi leading the chart followed by Lagos island, VI this is true because we know that these towns have houses where the elites, celebrity lives.

Figure 8. Average Price of Houses by State

Figure 9. 10 Expensive Houses by Town (with cleaned dataset)

Figure 10. Towns with Expensive Houses in Lagos

Results

```

Detached Duplex          1172
Terraced Duplexes        271
Semi Detached Duplex    235
Detached Bungalow       148
Block of Flats           73
Semi Detached Bungalow  30
Terraced Bungalow       12
Name: house types, dtype: int64

```


(a) counts of building in Ajah Lagos

(b) chart showing price of building in Ajah

Figure 11. Counts and Prices of Different Building in Ajah

The diagram below shows the relationship between price and number of bedrooms, the correlation coefficient is 0.48 which shows that they are moderately correlated.

Figure 12. Correlation Between Bedroom and Price

	bedrooms	bathrooms	toilets	parking_space	total_rooms
bedrooms	1.000000	0.718953	0.741145	0.264946	0.827785
bathrooms	0.718953	1.000000	0.801250	0.287814	0.862077
toilets	0.741145	0.801250	1.000000	0.263363	0.859545
parking_space	0.264946	0.287814	0.263363	1.000000	0.628501
total_rooms	0.827785	0.862077	0.859545	0.628501	1.000000
price	0.474978	0.381313	0.391996	0.170141	0.434678

	price
bedrooms	0.474978
bathrooms	0.381313
toilets	0.391996
parking_space	0.170141
total_rooms	0.434678
price	1.000000

Figure 13. Correlation Matrix Between Different Variables

From this plot and correlation matrix, we can see that some variables are highly correlated they can affect our analysis. It can be seen that bedrooms, bathrooms, toilets are highly correlated, this is possible as the number of bedroom increases, the number of bathrooms and toilets tend to increase. We can use VIF to test multicollinearity. (see Etaga et al [19]).

Figure 14. Heat Map Showing the Correlation Between Variables

	variables	VIF
0	bedrooms	inf
1	bathrooms	inf
2	parking_space	inf
3	total_rooms	inf
4	toilets	inf

(a) 1st ViF

	variables	VIF
0	bedrooms	150.847725
1	bathrooms	198.881366
2	parking_space	66.876100
3	total_rooms	920.254414

(b) Vif after dropping toilet

	variables	VIF
0	bedrooms	39.268549
1	bathrooms	40.124334
2	parking_space	10.411690

(c) vif after dropping total room

	variables	VIF
0	bedrooms	9.680981
1	parking_space	9.680981

(d) vif after dropping bathroom

Figure 15. VIF Before and After

As predicted from the correlation matrix, it can be observed that in Variance Inflation Factors Results (VIFs), 5 of the independent variable's VIF's exceeded 10, which indicate very strong presence of multicollinearity, dropping some of these columns reduce the value of the vif. A boxplot for the distribution of Ajah house price was plotted and it was discovered that there were outliers and it was trimmed using quantiles. The research model is specified thus $price = f(\text{number of bedrooms, number of parking space, house-type})$.

Figure 16. Boxplot of Ajah House Price

After cleaning this data, I built the model, to build a model for prediction there are three stages which include:

1. Splitting the data: This involves splitting the data into features and target. In python we call the predictors (independent variable) Features while the dependent variable is referred to as Target. The predictor involved in this analysis is bathrooms, parking-space, house types. The dependent variable is price. These data are further splitted into TRAIN-TEST SPLIT

(a) Train-test split: A train test split is when you split your data into a training set and a testing set. The training set is used for training the model, and the testing set is used to test your model. This allows you to train your models on the training set, and then test their accuracy on the unseen testing set. The data was splitted into two sets. 80% for training and 20% for testing. Having (1292, 3) for training and (323, 3) for testing. This ensures that both sets are representative of the entire dataset, and

gives a good way to measure the accuracy of the models.

- (b) Fitting the model: This involves making a pipeline, in pipeline we can have many transformers but one regressor which comes at the end of the pipeline and then fitting it with our data.

Figure 17. Fitting a Model

The pipeline has a:

- Transformer which takes a dataset as an input and creates an augmented dataset as output. In this analysis OneHotEncoder is used to encode categorical data (House-types) to numerical data
- Estimator: An estimator in machine learning is an algorithm that fits on the input dataset to generate a model, which is a transformer. Regression is an estimator that trains on a dataset with labels and features and produces a ridge regression model.

2. Baselines: A baseline model is essentially a simple model that acts as a reference in a machine learning project used for comparison purpose. for regression problems, the common rule is to create baseline models that predict the mean or median of the training data output. In the model the mean-apt-price which is the mean of y train is 58429682.66 and Baseline MAE which is the mae of y -pred-baseline and y train is 12644596.9. from the baseline model: it shows that if we predicted that the price of an

apartment is N58429682.66 then our prediction we would be off by an average N12644596.9.

Mean absolute error(MAE) is a performance metric in the context of machine learning, absolute error refers to the magnitude of difference between the prediction of an observation and the true value of that observation given as:

$$MAE = \frac{\sum |y - \hat{y}|}{n} \quad (4)$$

The Training MAE 8986866.53, this shows that training mae beats the baseline mae by N3657730 it is useful to predict house price. The next step is to use it on set of data that it has not seen before which is our test set. Test MAE: 8525486.28 The test mae also beats our baseline mae.

3. Evaluating and communicating results: Ability to communicate results to the stake holders.

Fig18 shows the predicted value of price y^{\wedge} against y test price.

The regression equation is given as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Price} = & 33722523.23 + 4352474.19 * \text{bedrooms} \\ & + 111280.33 * \text{parking-space} + 12215882.35 * \text{DD} \\ & + 673130.34 * \text{SDD} \\ & + 4962884.93 * \text{BOF} + -3873523.72 * \text{TD} + - \\ & 3729909.35 * \text{DB} + -7236944.02 * \text{SDB} + - \\ & 3011520.53 * \text{TB} \text{ where} \end{aligned}$$

33722523.23: intercept

DD : Detached duplex

TD : Terraced duplex

SDD : semi detached duplex

BOF : Block of flat

SDB : semi detached bungalow

DB : Detached bungalow

TB : Terraced bungalow are all the coefficients.

Each one of these coefficient affects price either positively or negatively.

Communicate Results

Figure 18. Out Sampling

Figure 19. Feature Importance

Feature Importance refers to technique that calculates a score for all the input features for a given model—the scores simply represent the “importance” of each feature. A higher score means that the specific feature will have a larger effect on the model that is being used to predict a certain variable. This shows that when the

house is a detached duplex the price increases by N12.5 million but when it is a semidetached duplex the price decreases by N7.5million, it also shows that parking space add little amount to the price of an apartment in Ajah and the number of bedrooms also increases the house price by N2.5 million.

Figure 20. Predicted Price of Different House Types

Discussion

The outcome of this study was reached utilizing a regression model with three stages, including data splitting, baseline modeling for comparison, and result evaluation, as seen in figures 18.0 and 19.0 above. The price of the house increases by N12.5 million when it is a detached duplex, but decreases by N1 million when it is a semidetached duplex.

Conclusion

In this article, machine learning models have been deployed to predict house prices in Lagos Nigeria. Ikoyi Lagos state has the most expensive house in Nigeria followed by Maitama district Abuja. From the feature importance, it shows that house type plays an important role in predicting the price of a building. This shows

that when the house is a detached duplex the price increases by N12.5 million but when it is a semidetached duplex the price decreases by a million, it also shows that parking space adds a little amount to the price of an apartment in Ajah and the number of bedrooms also increases the house price by 2.5 million.

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